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METHODS FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Education particularly higher education is the most crucial sector for leveraging the growth and development of the nation in social, economic, cultural, political and scientific aspects. It is the basis of all national endeavors and development plans. Education provides strength and resilience to the people to respond to changing and often adverse situations. Education has the potential of transferring human beings into human resources. And thus potential development of human resource is the foremost function of education. Quality and excellence is of great significance both to the provider of higher education and education receiver in the process of building solid foundation of higher education and building capacities and capabilities of receivers, thus bridging the gap between underdeveloped and developed nation, rich and poor societies, less knowledgeable and erudite sections of population. Education has the ability to induce change leading to progress of society. Education has indeed become a subject of public policy and a sine qua non for the survival of society. In the realm of present day globalised world higher education is required to uphold creativity, talent, adaptability and quality. In order to fully utilize the fruits of higher education endeavours, the fundamental concern is to make sure that its quality and excellence are ensured, sustained and upgraded at all levels and appropriate policy measures are adopted to match our higher education system to international levels. The first section of the paper addresses the status of higher education in India. The second section focuses on the challenges faced by higher education institutions. The third section deals with the foremost policy initiatives by the government in the higher education sector. In the fourth section an attempt has been made to delineate imperative measures needed to foster quality and excellence in higher education. The paper strongly supports that the need of the present era is inclusive and qualitative expansion of higher education to uphold the cause for wide-ranging and all round development of the nation.

Keywords: Higher education, Tools and Technique, Quality improvement, Creativity and learning.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Higher education is very important in growing countries like India, because the countries entire development depends on the people with the innovative mind. Higher education is the process of learning, where the utility of skill cannot be achieved without the acquisition of previous skills or previous knowledge. Due to upgradation of modern learning technology and delivery models, the higher education system is slowly responding to the changes in the system and fails to anticipate or shape the career. The curriculum remains almost unchanged for decades. The system of evaluation focus on memory rather than understanding reducing learning and creativity. The educational technology services help students to take advantage of the wide array of technology that supports the need of students who learn differently. The overall growth of the country can be achieved by improving the quality of education what we provide. There are many important quality management, methods, tools and techniques that have been fully tried out in industry which could be adopted in the field of education such as digital class room, Students communication through social media, Improving faculty education, Experimental learning etc. Using these tools and techniques quality of an education can be polished and improved. This paper strongly supports the need of higher education and how to improve the quality of our country by using effective techniques and achieve higher goals in mere future. India has always been a place where you can see scholars and learners. In the ancient time of our country “Gurukul System” used to revolve around teaching and learning, where the students were educated under the guidance of Guru. In Gurukul System the students used to leave in the same house along with the Guru and all the students were considered equally irrespective of their social standing/ social status. The higher education system in India improved after the India got Independence. The Indian Education system highly uses English as a principal language of higher education and research and has an extensive academic tradition. Academic liberty is appreciated and there are a small number of high-quality institutions that can form the foundation of quality education. A good quality of higher education can be defined based on the outcomes of the students in the particular academic year [1]. It can be gained based on the knowledge, competence and orientation. Higher education is the most pivotal sector for strengthening the growth and development of the nation in social, economic, cultural, political and scientific aspects. The quality of Higher education of our country can be improved by improving the quality of Education in India. There are much important quality management, methods, tools and techniques that have been fully tried out in industry which could be adopted in the field of education such as digital class room, Students communication through social media, Improving faculty education, Experimental learning etc. [2]. Using these tools and techniques quality of an education can be polished and improved. Higher education system provides ample amount of opportunities to grow over the next decades if it is nourished wisely.

2. SCOPE OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA:

As higher education systems grow and diversify, society is mainly concentrating on quality of programmes, public assessments and international rankings of higher education institutions. [3] Due to the development of private organisation The government’s call to private players has widen the scope for Indian general masses to upgrade their competencies to get share in the global economy as an active stakeholders.[4]Online Education system is more likely to be accessed by the learner because its having the simplest feature which is overtaken the text books or offline materials .It is easily accessible, clearly organized, well written and has a facilitated

learning environment. to provide and support the concept online/open education government has taken many initiative programmes [5] Online education is essentially the gateway to multifaceted development and prosperity in the country. Scientific, technological and economical evolution of a country are as dependent on the higher education system as they are on the working class and are on the prior list of the advancement.[6]. Higher education is now under the pioneering list of the government. It is under booming stage in many countries, including in India, managing the massive expansion that are available for higher education has become challenging for governments and regulatory bodies alike.[7]

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The core objective of this study is to understand the overall perspective of higher education in India. This paper also examines the methods, tools or techniques to improve quality of higher education. The paper also speaks to provide simple, universal access to information and services for all faculties, staffs and students.

4. ATTRITION IN HIGHER EDUCATION:

The most frequent problem that is found in higher education is lack of quick adaption and also it is observed that the students are not being able to connect to the knowledge that have be learned through online or offline education system. If this is the first issues, the second problem is that they don't know where to actually implement the knowledge in the real life [8]. The advancement of technology has made it simpler to adapt knowledge virtually but at the same time the learners are not able to make optimum utilization of resources. Lacks of placing the requirements of the faculties by the universities, faculties are not able to focus on each and every student [9]. Due to this the performances of students as well as the faculties both are hampered. Due to poor qualities of skills and knowledge large amount of educated people are facing unemployment in India.

5. BREAKTHROUGHS TOWARDS IMPROVING QUALITIES OF HIGHER EDUCATION:

Although there are so many advanced technologies adopted by Indian education system, Universities still follow up the old syllabus contents and also probably learning is less than their capabilities [10]. Even organisations complain that although there is higher number of candidates graduating every year, they have the deficiency in basic skills such as writing, problem solving and using the common sense. [11] Lack of training provided to the faculties' effect the teaching skills and also faculties find great difficulty in adapting the new facilities available in the education system. [12] Research in Higher education institution is at its lowest diminishing stage. There is no proper financial support for the higher education form the government and society [13, 14]. Teaching quality cannot be measured by the qualification on credentials possessed by a teacher but it is actually measured in terms of his performance in the classroom environment [15] Teaching strategy adopted by teacher is the indicator of his quality and which can also be measured in terms of student's achievement. Further the speed of a teacher can be measured by the speed of slowest learner in his classroom environment. Teacher quality and pedagogical strategy is playing very important role in higher education which helps the students to succeed in real life [16].

6. SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITIES OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA:

In order to improve the quality of higher education in India the committee of higher education and the regulatory bodies must ensure that the basic minimum standards of technical educations to be provided to meet the demand of industries [17]. The current generation are expecting professionalized courses to be offered by the higher education so that they get better opportunities in the industries to get employed to make the professionalized courses more attractive the teachers and the researchers has to be offered good incentives. The education system has to be altered right from the primary education to higher education in order to have the global competency [18]. Industry and students are expecting specialized courses to be offered so that they get the latest and best in education and they are also industry ready and employable. Vocational and Diploma courses need to be made more attractive to facilitate specialized programs being offered to students. Incentives should be provided to teachers and researchers to make these professions more attractive for the younger generation. Industry and students are expecting specialized courses to be offered so that they get the latest and best in education and they are also industry ready and employable. Vocational and Diploma courses need to be made more attractive to facilitate specialized programs being offered to students. Incentives should be provided to teachers and researchers to make these professions more attractive for the younger generation.

7. CONCLUSION:

This paper reveals the current scenario of higher education in India. [19] The above-mentioned suggestions such as providing training and updating syllabus and also providing better incentives are considered as important tools. There are ample number of opportunities available, but there is an issue in accessing or utilizing it [20]. There is a necessity to recheck the Quality Standards, Financial Resources, Access and Equity, infrastructure.

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